

Decoupling Neutrino Magnetic Moment from Mass with $SU(2)_L$ Invariance

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Part I: Electromagnetic properties of neutrinos

- Neutrinos are **electrically neutral** in the SM; they do not have direct coupling to photons.
- **Radiative (loop) corrections** may induce electromagnetic properties — such as charge radius, and electric and **magnetic moments** — of neutrinos.

- Effective electromagnetic vertex with form factors:

$$\bar{\nu}_k \Lambda_{\mu}^{kj} \nu_j A^{\mu}$$

$$\Lambda_{fi}^{\mu}(q) = (\gamma^{\mu} - q^{\mu} \not{q} / q^2) \left[\boxed{F_{fi}^Q(q^2)} + \boxed{F_{fi}^A(q^2)} q^2 \gamma_5 \right] - i\sigma^{\mu\nu} q_{\nu} \left[\boxed{F_{fi}^M(q^2)} + \boxed{iF_{fi}^E(q^2)} \gamma_5 \right]$$

charge

anapole

magnetic

electric

q

a

μ

ε

chirality-conserving

chirality-flipping

- $\mu_{\nu} = F_M(0) \implies \nu$ magnetic moment

Physical processes with a Neutrino Magnetic Moments

- **Neutrino decay:**

$$\Gamma_{\nu_i \rightarrow \nu_f + \gamma} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \left(\frac{m_i^2 - m_f^2}{m_i} \right)^3 |\mu_{fi}|^2$$

In the simplest extensions of the SM, the $\mu_\nu < 10^{-23} \mu_B$ and lifetime is of order $10^{46} s$ for eV mass.

- **Plasmon decay into pair of neutrinos:**

$$\Gamma_{\gamma^* \rightarrow \nu \bar{\nu}}(\mu_\nu) = \frac{\mu_\nu^2}{24\pi} Z \frac{\omega_P^4}{\omega_\gamma}$$

Plasma frequency

$$\omega_\gamma^2 - \vec{k}_\gamma^2 = \omega_P^2$$

[Bernstein J, Ruderman M, Feinberg G '63]

- **Spin-flavor precession**

$$i \frac{d}{dr} \begin{pmatrix} \nu \\ \bar{\nu} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & B_\perp M \\ -B_\perp M & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu \\ \bar{\nu} \end{pmatrix}$$

Physical processes with a Neutrino Magnetic Moments

• Scattering

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{dT_e}\right)_{\text{Tot}} \equiv \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dT}\right)_{\text{SM}} + \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dT}\right)_{\text{mag}}$$

T is the electron recoil energy

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{dT}\right)_{\text{SM}} = \frac{G_{\text{F}}^2 m_e}{2\pi} \left[(g_V + g_A)^2 + (g_V - g_A)^2 \left(1 - \frac{T}{E_\nu}\right)^2 + (g_A^2 - g_V^2) \frac{m_e T}{E_\nu^2} \right]$$

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma_{\nu e^-}}{dT_e}\right)_{\text{mag}} = \frac{\pi\alpha^2}{m_e^2} \left(\frac{1}{T_e} - \frac{1}{E_\nu}\right) \left(\frac{\mu_\nu}{\mu_B}\right)^2$$

Observable μ_ν is an effective parameter that depends on neutrino flavor composition at the detector

[Balantekin, Vassh, '13; Giunti, Studenikin, '24]

Limits on Neutrino Magnetic Moments

Method	Experiment	Limit [μ_B]	CL	Year
Reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ E ν ES	Krasnoyarsk	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 2.4 \times 10^{-10}$	90%	1992
	Rovno	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 1.9 \times 10^{-10}$	95%	1993
	MUNU	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 9 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2005
	TEXONO	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 7.4 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2006
	GEMMA	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 2.9 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2012
	CONUS	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 7.5 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2022
	LUX-ZEPLIN (74)	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 1.5 \times 10^{-11}$ $\mu_{\nu_\mu} < 2.3 \times 10^{-11}$ $\mu_{\nu_\tau} < 2.1 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2022
Solar E ν ES	XENONnT (71)	$\mu_{\nu_e} < 9.0 \times 10^{-12}$ $\mu_{\nu_\mu} < 1.5 \times 10^{-11}$ $\mu_{\nu_\tau} < 1.3 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2022
	LUX-ZEPLIN (74) + PandaX-4T (78) +	$\mu_S^{\text{LE}} < 7.5 \times 10^{-12}$ $\mu_{\nu_e} < 1.0 \times 10^{-11}$	90%	2023

- The energy loss of the red giant branch in the globular cluster provides the most stringent limit of $\mu_{\text{astro}} < 4.5 \times 10^{-12} \mu_B$

Viaux ++, '13

[see the review by Giunti, Studenikin, '24]

Limits on Neutrino Magnetic Moments

- Current Experiment can reach sensitivity of $\mu_\nu \sim 10^{-11} \mu_B$

- Any extension of SM:

$$\mu_\nu < 10^{-19} \mu_B \text{ (more on it later !)}$$

- Gap of 8 orders of magnitude

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μ_ν in BSM

Dirac neutrinos:

SM + ν_R with $\Delta L = 0$

$$\mathcal{L}_Y : y_\nu \bar{L} H \nu_R + h.c.$$

To forbid Majorana mass term for ν_R

- Effective dimension-5 operator after electroweak symmetry for Dirac neutrinos (couples LH and RH neutrinos)

$$\frac{1}{2} (\mu_\nu^D)_{\alpha\beta} \bar{\nu}_L^\alpha \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_R^\beta F_{\mu\nu}$$

Electromagnetic field strength tensor

- Dirac neutrinos with **diagonal** and **off-diagonal (transition)** magnetic moments

Transition μ_ν are GIM suppressed

$$\mu_{kk}^D \simeq 3.2 \times 10^{-19} \mu_B \left(\frac{m_k}{\text{eV}} \right)$$

$$\mu_{kj}^D \simeq -3.9 \times 10^{-23} \mu_B \left(\frac{m_k + m_j}{\text{eV}} \right) \sum_{\ell=e,\mu,\tau} U_{\ell k}^* U_{\ell j} \frac{m_\ell^2}{m_\tau^2}$$

$$\mu_{kj}^D \simeq \frac{3eG_F}{16\sqrt{2}\pi^2} (m_k + m_j) \left(\delta_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\ell=e,\mu,\tau} U_{\ell k}^* U_{\ell j} \frac{m_\ell^2}{m_W^2} \right)$$

Suppressed by neutrino mass

[Fujikawa, Shrock, '80; Pal, Wolfenstein, '82; Shrock, '82; ...]

μ_ν in BSM

Left-Right Symmetric Model:

- In LRSM (based on gauge group $SU(2)_L \otimes SU(2)_R \otimes U(1)_{B-L}$) ν_R has gauge interaction with W_R and $W_L - W_R$ mixing ($\sin \xi$) leads to magnetic moment of neutrinos

$$\mu_\nu \simeq \frac{eG_F m_\ell}{4\sqrt{2}\pi^2} \sin 2\xi$$

[Shrock, '74; Kim '76;...]

- Same diagram **without photon** leads to neutrino mass!

$$\implies \mu_\nu < 10^{-16} \mu_B$$

μ_ν in BSM

Majorana neutrinos

- Effective dimension-5 operator after electroweak symmetry for Majorana neutrinos

$$\frac{1}{4}(\mu_\nu^M)_{\alpha\beta} \bar{\nu}_{\alpha L}^C \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_{\beta L} F_{\mu\nu}$$

Antisymmetric in flavor indices

- The magnetic moment are suppressed as in Dirac case in the minimal extension of the SM with Majorana neutrino masses

$$\mu_{kj}^M \simeq -7.8 \times 10^{-23} \mu_B \left(\frac{m_k + m_j}{\text{eV}} \right) \sum_{\ell=e,\mu,\tau} U_{\ell k}^* U_{\ell j} \frac{m_\ell^2}{m_\tau^2}$$

Suppressed by neutrino mass

[Shrock, '82; ..]

Difficult to generate neutrino magnetic moment without its corresponding mass

μ_ν and m_ν conundrum: general argument

- The neutrino magnetic operator and mass are both **chirality flipping operator**
- The effective vertex that generates the dipole operator (neutrino magnetic moment) in any EFT **in general** give rise to neutrino masses **once the photon line is removed.**

Λ is the new physics scale; mass of heavy particles running inside the loop

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Λ is the new physics scale; mass of heavy particles running inside the loop

- At least one new particles running inside the loop must be of $\mathcal{O}(100)$ GeV

\implies leads to the naturalness bound

$$\mu_\nu \lesssim 10^{-19} \mu_B \left(\frac{\delta m_\nu}{0.1 \text{ eV}} \right) \left(\frac{\Lambda}{\text{TeV}} \right)^{-2}$$

Mechanisms to decouple mass and moment

- **Spin Symmetry**

Barr, Freire, and Zee (1990)

Babu, Chang, Keung, Phillips (1992)

- **Voloshin Symmetry / $SU(2)_H$ Horizontal Symmetry**

Voloshin (1988)

Barbari and Mohapatra (1989)

Babu and Mohapatra (1990)

Leurer and Marcus (1990)

- **The proposed mechanism: $SU(2)_L$ Invariance**

Pages, Thapa; arXiv: 2506.15777

Spin Suppression Mechanism

- Uses **spin** quantum number of the photon

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- The original proposal uses charged singlet h^+ (1,1,1) and three scalar doublets ϕ_a (1,2,1/2)

$$\delta m_{\nu_\mu \nu_\tau} = 0.5 \times 10^6 \text{ eV} \left(\frac{m_\tau^2}{M_W^2} \right) \left(\frac{\delta M_2^2 + \delta M_3^2}{2M^2} \right) \left(\frac{M}{\text{TeV}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\mu_\nu}{10^{-12} \mu_B} \right)$$

requires $\lesssim 10^{-3}$

Barr, Freire, and Zee (1990)

Babu, Chang, Keung, Phillips (1992)

Horizontal Symmetry

- Voloshin $SU(2)_\nu$ symmetry that transforms $(\nu_R^C, \nu_L)^T$ as doublets with the transformation $\nu_L \rightarrow \nu_R^C$, $\nu_R \rightarrow -\nu_L^C$ such that **magnetic moment is invariant while mass term is not.**

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\nu}_L \nu_R &\rightarrow -\bar{\nu}_L \nu_R \\ \bar{\nu}_L \sigma_{\mu\nu} \nu_R F^{\mu\nu} &\rightarrow +\bar{\nu}_L \sigma_{\mu\nu} \nu_R F^{\mu\nu}\end{aligned}$$

Simplest realization in $SU(3)_L \times U(1)_X$
 $\implies \mu_\nu \lesssim 10^{-16} \mu_B$

Barbari and Mohapatra (1989)

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- **Horizontal symmetry:** Based on $SU(3)_C \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y \times SU(2)_H$

$$\Psi_L = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_e & \nu_\mu \\ e & \mu \end{pmatrix}_L, \Psi_R = (e \ \mu)_R, \Psi_{3L} = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_\tau \\ \tau \end{pmatrix}_L, \tau_R \quad \Phi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1^+ & \phi_2^+ \\ \phi_1^0 & \phi_2^0 \end{pmatrix}, \phi_s = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_s^+ \\ \phi_s^0 \end{pmatrix}, \eta = (\eta_1^+ \ \eta_2^+), \sigma_a = (\sigma_1^0 \ \sigma_2^0 \ \sigma_3^0)_a$$

$\implies \mu_\nu \lesssim 10^{-12} \mu_B$

$$\left(\frac{\mu_{\nu_e \nu_\mu}}{10^{-12} \mu_B} \right) = 2 \left(\frac{\delta m_{\nu_e \nu_\mu}}{\text{eV}} \right) \left(\frac{\text{GeV}^2}{\Delta m_\eta^2} \right) \left(\frac{m_\eta^2}{m_\phi^2} - 1 \right) \log \frac{m_\eta^2}{m_\phi^2}$$

Babu and Mohapatra (1990)

The proposed mechanism: $SU(2)_L$ Invariance

- The Dirac (Majorana) neutrino magnetic moment arises from **dimension-6 (dimension-7) operators**

$$C_{\nu B} g_1 \bar{L} \tilde{H} \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_R B_{\mu\nu} + C_{\nu W} g_2 \bar{L} \tau^a \tilde{H} \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_R W_{\mu\nu}^a \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \bar{\nu}_L \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_R F_{\mu\nu}$$

$$C_{LHB} g_1 (\bar{L}^c \epsilon H) \sigma^{\mu\nu} (H^T \epsilon L) B_{\mu\nu} + C_{LHW} g_2 (\bar{L}^c \epsilon H) \sigma^{\mu\nu} (H^T \epsilon \tau^i L) W_{\mu\nu}^i \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \bar{\nu}_L^c \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_L F_{\mu\nu}$$

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- Both L and H transform as doublets under $SU(2)_L$: $H \sim (1, 2, 1/2)$ and $L \sim (1, 2, -1/2)$

$$2 \otimes 2 = 3 \oplus 1$$

 combine to form gauge-invariant operators with B_μ and W_μ
singlet

triplet

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- Replace L with new Fermion transforming under different representation of $SU(2)_L$: $\mathbf{R}_{1,2}$

Search for effective vertices that **contain an invariant in the product**

$$\mathbf{R}_1 \otimes \mathbf{R}_2 \otimes 3 \otimes 2 \otimes \dots \otimes 2$$

n

$$3 : W_\mu^i$$

but not in the product

$$2 : H$$

$$\mathbf{R}_1 \otimes \mathbf{R}_2 \otimes 2 \otimes \dots \otimes 2$$

n

Complete set of diagrams

- Dipole operator **exists only for** the $SU(2)_L$ gauge bosons W_μ **but not for** the $U(1)_Y$ gauge boson B_μ
- Neutrino mass without any gauge boson attached is **group theoretically identical** to the B_μ graph
 \implies **vanishes due to $SU(2)_L$ gauge invariance**

**Condition to realize magnetic moment
through W_μ together with vanishing mass
contribution**

$$|R_1 - R_2| - n = 2$$

$$k = R_{1,2} - 2 \text{ to connect to } L$$

$$k = R_{1,2} - 1 \text{ to connect to } \nu_R$$

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Minimal Model: Dirac

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$$\frac{\mu_\nu^D}{\mu_B} = 2\sqrt{2} m_e \nu C_{\nu W}$$

$$C_{\nu W} = \frac{y_\Psi y_\delta y_T^* m_S^2 \left(1 - \log \left(m_S^2 / m_\Psi^2 \right) \right) - m_\Psi^2}{16\pi^2 (m_\Psi^2 - m_S^2)^2}$$

For $m_\Psi, m_S \sim 1 \text{ TeV}$, $y_\delta, y_T \sim 1$; $y_\Psi \sim 10^{-3}$
 $\implies \mu_\nu^D \sim 10^{-12} \mu_B$

Non-Minimal models

Case	$SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$	$U(1)_L$	Relevant Lagrangian \mathcal{L}	$m_\nu \left[\frac{\mu_\nu}{\mu_B m_e} \right]$	Enhanced μ_ν ?
a	$\Psi \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{3}, 0)$	1	$\mathcal{L}_a = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \bar{\Psi}_R \Psi_L + \bar{L} \tilde{H} \Psi_R + \bar{L} \tilde{H} \nu_R$	–	✗
b	$F \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, 1/2)$	1	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R H \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L H \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L H \nu_R$	$-\frac{3}{2} m_\Psi^2 - 4\pi^2 v^2$	✗
c	$S \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{3}, 0)$	0	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{\Psi}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{\Psi}_L S \nu_R + H^\dagger H S$	$-\frac{1}{4} y_\Psi ^2 v^2$	✓
d	$\{S, F\} \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{4}, 3/2)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L S \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L S \nu_R + S^\dagger H^3$	0	✓
e	$\{S, F\} \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, 1/2, -)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L S \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L S \nu_R + H^\dagger S S^\dagger H$	0	✓

- The magnetic moment **can be much larger**, as the neutrino mass remain **zero at least up to one-loop generated dimension-6 operators**.

For $m_\Psi, m_S, m_F \sim 1 \text{ TeV}$,
 $y_\delta, y_T, y_\Psi \sim 1$

- Lightest particle can serve as a dark matter candidate.

Conclusion

- A **novel mechanism** for generating large neutrino magnetic moment, in which the associated **mass contribution is forbidden by $SU(2)_L$ invariance** was proposed.
- Explicit **UV completions was provided** that yield neutrino magnetic moments within the **sensitivity of current and future experiments**.

Thank you

Backup Slides

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New Fermion acts as a bridge between effective vertex and SM fermions

Minimal UV Realization: Majorana Magnetic moment

Topology	Rep. in loop	$\supset 1$	$\supset 3$
(a)	$1 \otimes 1$	✓	✗
	$1 \otimes 3$ or $3 \otimes 1$	✗	✓
	$3 \otimes 3$	✓	✓
(b)	$1 \otimes 2 \otimes 2$	✓	✓
	$3 \otimes 2 \otimes 2$	✓	✓
(c)	$2 \otimes 2$	✓	✓
	$4 \otimes 2$	✗	✓
(d)	$2 \otimes 2 \otimes 2 \otimes 2$	✓	✓

Model for Majorana

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{L,R} &\sim (1,1,0) \\
 \Psi_{L,R} &\sim (1,3,0) \\
 S &\sim (1,3,0) \\
 \Phi &\sim (1,2,1/2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\mu_\nu^M}{\mu_B} = 4 m_e v^2 C_{LHW}$$

$$C_{LHW} = \frac{y_\Psi^* y_\delta y_T y'_N \theta_{\Phi H}}{16\pi^2} \frac{m_\Psi^2 + m_S^2 \left(\log(m_S^2/m_\Psi^2) - 1 \right)}{m_N (m_\Psi^2 - m_S^2)^2}$$

$$m_\nu^{\text{loop}} = - \frac{\mu_\nu^M}{\mu_B} \frac{|y_\Psi|^2 v^2}{8m_e}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{For } m_\Psi, m_S \sim 1 \text{ TeV}, m_N \sim 100 \text{ GeV} \\
 &y_\delta, y_T, y_N \sim 1; y_\Psi \sim 10^{-3} \\
 &\implies \mu_\nu^M \sim 10^{-12} \mu_B
 \end{aligned}$$

RGE-Induced Contribution

$$C_{\nu B} g_1 \bar{L} \tilde{H} \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_R B_{\mu\nu}$$

$$C_{\nu W} g_2 \bar{L} \tau^a \tilde{H} \sigma^{\mu\nu} \nu_R W_{\mu\nu}^a$$

$$C_{\nu H} (\bar{L} \tilde{H} \nu_R) (H^\dagger H)$$

The RGEs for the Wilson coefficients

$$\mu \frac{d}{d\mu} C_i^6(\mu) = \frac{1}{16\pi^2} \sum_j \gamma_{ij} C_j^6(\mu)$$

- The one-loop β -function coefficients in the momentum range $\nu < \mu < \Lambda$

$$\gamma_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 3\pi(\alpha_1 - 3\alpha_2 + 4\alpha_t) & -18\pi\alpha_2 & 0 \\ -6\pi\alpha_1 & -3\pi(\alpha_1 - 3\alpha_2 - 4\alpha_t) & 0 \\ -3(4\pi)^2\alpha_1(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) & 3(4\pi)^2\alpha_2(\alpha_1 + 3\alpha_2) & 12\lambda - 9\pi(\alpha_1 + 3\alpha_2 - 4\alpha_t) \end{pmatrix}$$

- For Dirac Magnetic moment, it leads to the bound $\mu_\nu^D \lesssim 10^{-15} \mu_B$.

[Bell et al, hep-ph/0504134]

- Can do similar analysis for Majorana Magnetic moment which leads to the bound

$$\mu_\nu^M \lesssim 10^{-10} \mu_B.$$

[Bell et al, hep-ph/0606248]

Minimal models

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b	$F \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, 1/2)$	1	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R H \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L H \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L H \nu_R$	$-\frac{3}{2} m_\Psi^2 - 4\pi^2 v^2$	✗
c	$S \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{3}, 0)$	0	$\mathcal{L}_a + \Psi_R S \Psi_L + \Psi_L S \nu_R + H^\dagger H S$	$-\frac{1}{4} y_\Psi ^2 v^2$	✓
d	$\{S, F\} \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{4}, 3/2)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L S \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L S \nu_R + S^\dagger H^3$	0	✓
e	$\{S, F\} \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, 1/2, -)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L S \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L S \nu_R + H^\dagger S S^\dagger H$	0	✓

Minimal models: Realistic case

Case	$SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$	$U(1)_L$	Relevant Lagrangian \mathcal{L}	$m_\nu \left[\frac{\mu_\nu}{\mu_B m_e} \right]$	Enhanced μ_ν ?
a	$\Psi \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{3}, 0)$	1	$\mathcal{L}_a = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} + \bar{\Psi}_R \Psi_L + \bar{L} \tilde{H} \Psi_R + \bar{L} \tilde{H} \nu_R$	–	X
b	$F \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, 1/2)$	1	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R H \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L H \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L H \nu_R$	$-\frac{3}{5} m_\Psi^2 - 4\pi^2 v^2$	X
c	$S \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{3}, 0)$	0	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{\Psi}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{\Psi}_L S \nu_R + H^\dagger H S$	$-\frac{1}{4} y_\Psi ^2 v^2$	✓
d	$\{S, F\} \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{4}, 3/2)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L S \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L S \nu_R + S^\dagger H^3$	0	✓
e	$\{S, F\} \sim (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, 1/2, -)$	$\{0, 1\}$	$\mathcal{L}_a + \bar{F}_R F_L + \bar{F}_R S \Psi_L + \bar{F}_L S \Psi_R + \bar{F}_L S \nu_R + H^\dagger S S^\dagger H$	0	✓

$$C_{\nu H} = 2C_{\nu W} |y_\Psi|^2$$

$$m_\nu^{\text{loop}} = - \frac{\mu_\nu^D |y_\Psi|^2 v^2}{\mu_B 4m_e}$$

For $m_\Psi, m_S \sim 1 \text{ TeV}$, $y_\delta, y_T \sim 1$; $y_\Psi \sim 10^{-3}$
 $\implies \mu_\nu^D \sim 10^{-12} \mu_B$